

REPORT

The XXIV Conference “Classification and Data Analysis – Theory and Applications” 14-16 September 2015, Gdańsk, Poland

The Section on Classification and Data Analysis of the Polish Statistical Association (SKAD) held its conference from 14th to 16th of September 2015 in Gdańsk. It was XXIV Conference “Classification and Data Analysis – Theory and Applications”. The conference was jointly organized by SKAD and Department of Statistics of University of Gdańsk. The organizing committee was chaired by Professor dr hab. Mirosław Szreder and dr hab. Krzysztof Najman, supported by dr hab. Kamila Migdał Najman, dr hab. Anna Zamojska and Mrs. Anna Nowicka. The conference was financially supported by the National Bank of Poland.

The following theoretical and applied areas were covered by the conference:

- a) theory – taxonomy, discriminant analysis, linear ordering methods, multivariate statistical analysis, methods of analysis of continuous, discrete and symbolic data, graphical methods;
- b) applications – financial data, marketing data, spatial data, and other applications in medicine, psychology, archaeology, etc., and computer applications of statistical methods.

The main objective of the conference was the presentation of scientific results in the area of theory and applications of classification and data analysis problems. It serves as an annual forum to discuss recent developments in the above areas as well as to identify and suggest some directions for future research agenda.

The conference was attended by 81 researchers from the following universities: University of Economics in Katowice, Cracow University of Economics, Poznań University of Economics, Wrocław University of Economics, University of Gdańsk, AGH University of Science and Technology in Cracow, Łódź University of Technology, Gdańsk University of Technology, Opole University of Technology, Wrocław University of Technology, Warsaw University of Life Sciences – SGGW, Warsaw School of Economics, Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce, University of Łódź, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Poznań University of Life Sciences, University of Szczecin, University of Białystok. Also, representatives of the National Bank of Poland and PBS market research company, participated in the conference.

During two plenary sessions and 13 parallel sessions there were 58 papers presented covering both theoretical and applied problems of classification and data analysis. In addition, 14 posters were presented during the poster session.

Sessions were chaired by the following professors: Józef Pocięcha, Eugeniusz Gatnar, Tadeusz Trzaskalik, Krzysztof Jajuga, Marek Walesiak, Barbara Pawełek, Feliks Wysocki, Ewa Roszkowska, Andrzej Sokołowski, Andrzej Bąk, Tadeusz Kufel, Mirosław Krzyśko, Krzysztof Najman, Małgorzata Rószkiewicz and Mirosław Szreder.

On the first day of the conference an annual meeting of members of SKAD took place, chaired by Professor Józef Pocięcha. During this meeting the following issues were discussed:

- A. Report on the activities of the members of the Section on Classification and Data Analysis of Polish Statistical Association – there are 231 members. The most important activities included:
 - participation in the International Federation of Classification Societies conference in Bologna – 19 persons presented 15 papers at that conference;
 - participation in the European Conference on Data Analysis in Colchester – 18 persons presented 15 papers.
- B. Information about upcoming conferences.
- C. Organization of the next SKAD conference – it will be organized by the Department of Statistical Methods at the University of Łódź.
- D. Election of SKAD representative to International Federation of Classification Societies Council. Professor Andrzej Sokołowski was elected for the 2016-2019 term.
- E. Discussion about future activities of SKAD.

Prepared by:

Krzysztof Jajuga

Marek Walesiak